

Disqualification Rhetoric in a Polarising Landscape: The Peruvian Case

Cambridge Journal of Political
Affairs
Volume 6, Issue 1 (2025): 69-80
© The Author(s) 2025
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16621282
cambridgepoliticalaffairs.co.uk

Luciana Antonella Barreto
University of Amsterdam

This paper studies disqualifying rhetoric used by Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo in the 2021 Peruvian presidential election. By elaborating from a qualitative thematic analysis of a TV debate, the study explains how the candidates used different rhetorical techniques to undermine each other, thus reflecting and reinforcing the social divisions in Peru. The analysis identifies 4 main themes: Fujimori's overt identity-based disqualifications targeting Castillo's identity; Castillo's covert contrast disqualifications emphasising policy and anti-elite narratives; mutual critiques of the prior government's handling of the COVID-19 pandemic; and pervasive overt disqualifications focused on corruption accusations. Such results highlight how disqualifying rhetoric not only shaped voter perceptions but amplified polarisation, aligning with framing theory and theories of negative campaigning. Ultimately, this study contributes to understanding the relationship between political rhetoric and social polarisation in electoral contexts, representing better implications for democratic governance in Latin America.

INTRODUCTION

In today's increasingly polarised political climate, during elections, candidates may opt to sway voters by transcending policy discussions and charitable initiatives, delving into negative rhetoric that reinforces and deepens existing cleavages (Lau and Rovner, 2009, p. 286). The 2021 Peruvian presidential election, placing Keiko Fujimori against Pedro Castillo, would showcase such dynamics. Keiko Fujimori, daughter of former president Alberto Fujimori, represents the continuation of a political dynasty associated with authoritarian governance, neoliberal reform, and a hardline stance on crime and insurgency (Burt, 2006). Her party, Fuerza Popular, has dominated Peru's legislature in recent years and is seen as emblematic of elite, urban interests (Dargent Bocanegra and Rousseau, 2021).

In contrast, Pedro Castillo rose to prominence as a rural teacher and union leader with no prior experience in national politics (Asensio et al, 2021, pp. 8-10). Representing Perú Libre, a Marxist-leaning party, Castillo campaigned on an anti-elite platform emphasising rural marginalisation, public investment, and national sovereignty over natural resources (Asensio et al, 2021). These sharply contrasting backgrounds not only shaped each candidate's campaign message but also reflected Peru's enduring structural divides, particularly the urban-rural and class-based cleavages that have defined political discourse since the civil conflict of the 1980s and 1990s.

Both candidates used disqualifying rhetoric—a key element of negative campaigning—to delegitimise their opponent's proposals or identity, resorting to polarising narratives of Peru's historical, social and political divides (Haselmayer, 2019, p. 256). On one end, Fujimori's rhetoric employed xenophobic undertones and accusations of left-wing insurgency sympathisers (Asensio et al., 2021, pp. 13-14). On the other end, Castillo emphasised anti-elite rhetoric and critiques of *Fujimorismo* (Asensio et al., 2021, pp. 13-14). Both tactics did not solely influence voter perceptions, but they also reflected the longstanding urban vs rural/urban divide (Asensio et al., 2021, pp. 13-14).

While Fujimori's campaign was scrutinised among scholars due to its divisive nature, particularly its identity-based disqualification of Castillo, less has been said about Castillo's rhetorical strategies and how they also shaped the polarised landscape (Escárzaga, 2022, p. 87). This gap limits our understanding of the interplay between negative campaigning and polarisation in Latin American democracies. To address this, this study examines a political debate through the process of a thematic analysis regarding the use of disqualifying rhetoric in the campaigns of Fujimori and Castillo through the lenses of negative political identities and framing theory. Identity-based disqualification often exploits societal divisions, including

ethnicity, geography or class. Candidates representing elites or majority groups might target identity to delegitimise opponents viewed as outsiders or threats to established norms. Conversely, policy-based disqualification is often employed in campaigns where governance records or ideological divides are central to the competition, allowing candidates to critique each other's plans or affiliations. In addition, this study theorises identity-based disqualification as not only a reflection of societal divides, but also a mechanism that deepens them, making it both a rhetorical tool and a structural issue in polarised democracies. These frameworks highlight the strategic choices certain candidates employ in polarising contexts.

This paper asks: *In what ways did Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo's campaigns manifest disqualifying rhetoric?* Following the hypothesised dynamics of disqualification use, for the Peruvian case, this research argues that Fujimori, representing elite continuity, would focus on identity disqualification, relying on direct recurrent attacks on Castillo's identity as an Andean man and his perceived radicalism in relation to insurgency groups. In contrast, Castillo, representing marginalised rural communities, would employ a mix of policy-based disqualification regarding critiques of *Fujimorismo* and identity-based disqualification on anti-elite narratives to challenge entrenched power structures in the country.

By analysing disqualifying rhetoric in this election, this research contributes to how negative campaigning reinforces societal divisions and influences voter alignments in polarised democracies. Within the Latin American context, it highlights how political campaigns reflect and exacerbate structural cleavages, providing insights into the broader implications of disqualifying rhetoric in democratic processes.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study examines the existing literature on disqualifying rhetoric within the frameworks of negative campaigning, polarisation, and framing theory to analyse the case of the 2021 Peruvian elections. Negative campaigning refers to the strategic focus on criticising opponents rather than promoting oneself (Lau and Rovner, 2009, p. 289). These criticisms often target an opponent's proposals, ideology, political record, failures, or even personal scandals (Lau and Rovner, 2009, p. 286).

A common tactic within negative campaigning is disqualification rhetoric, where candidates undermine opponents to weaken their public image (Escárzaga, 2022, pp. 78-79). Disqualification typically falls into two dimensions: policy-based and identity-based. Policy-based disqualification critiques an opponent's governance record, political alignment, policies, or leadership abilities (Haselmayer, 2019, pp. 356-357). Identity-based disqualification targets personal traits, ethnicity, social class, or geographic origin (Haselmayer, 2019). This rhetoric often aims to portray competitors as unfit or less qualified for political office, hence making it "disqualifying."

While the concept of disqualification within negative campaigning is widely accepted, its operationalisation remains contested (Lau and Rovner, 2009, pp. 289-290). Scholars often dichotomise political ads into "negative," emphasising criticism or disqualification, and "positive," focused on self-promotion (Lau and Rovner, 2009, pp. 289-290). However, such assumptions have been criticised for failing to distinguish legitimate attacks from "dirty" tactics or conflating contrast campaigns with outright attacks, leading to misleading conclusions on the contextual differences and rhetoric employed for specific cases (Jamieson et al., 2000, p. 44).

Building on this, framing theory offers a valuable lens for understanding how candidates strategically craft their rhetoric to influence public opinion. Framing involves highlighting certain aspects of reality while downplaying others, shaping the audience's interpretation of events, individuals, or issues (Entman, 1993, p. 52). In the context of negative campaigning, disqualification rhetoric serves as a framing strategy that emphasises an opponent's perceived flaws or incompatibility with societal norms, thereby reinforcing negative perceptions among voters.

However, framing theory is not without its critics when applied to the study of rhetoric. Some scholars argue that framing theory tends to focus disproportionately on the short-term effects of individual messages, often neglecting the cumulative impact of prior frames that have shaped broader divisive narratives. This oversight can limit the understanding of the contextual factors influencing public opinion if these historical frames are not adequately considered (Slater M.D., 2007, pp. 298-299).

When considering polarisation through disqualifying rhetoric as a form of negative campaigning, its impact becomes especially significant in divided societies. Peru's political landscape is particularly well-suited to the study of disqualifying rhetoric due to its entrenched historical cleavages. The country's long-standing rural-urban divide, racialised social hierarchies, and collective trauma from internal armed conflict in the 1980s and 1990s have left deep fault lines in public discourse (Burt, 2006, pp. 33-34). Rural and Indigenous populations, long excluded from political and economic power, are frequently framed as outsiders or threats in elite narratives, while urban elites are associated with corruption and neglect (Burt, 2006). The legacy of the Shining Path insurgency and state repression during the civil conflict has also entrenched a rhetorical arsenal—most notably *Terruqueo*, the practice of associating left-wing actors with terrorism—that continues to shape political polarisation (Burt, 2006). Disqualification rhetoric deepens societal cleavages by amplifying an "us vs. them" dynamic (McCoy et al., 2018, pp. 20-21). Polarisation itself is a multifaceted phenomenon, divided into ideological, affective, and factual belief dimensions, each of which has sparked scholarly debate (Iyengar et al., 2019, pp. 130-131; Rekker, 2021, p. 355). For instance, ideological polarisation focuses on the growing divergence of ideas into opposing extremes or the formation of broad, antagonistic coalitions (Jost et al., 2022, pp. 561-562; Dassonneville and Çakır, 2021, p.16). In contrast, affective polarisation emphasises divisions driven by social identity and the dehumanisation of opposing groups (Iyengar et al., 2019, p. 131).

For this research, therefore, a definition of polarisation that incorporates both ideological and affective dimensions is crucial. McCoy et al.'s (2018, pp. 20-21) framework captures this duality by examining how ideological polarisation—centred on policy and governance—and affective polarisation—rooted in social identity-driven divisions—interact to reinforce an "us vs. them" dynamic. This comprehensive perspective aligns with the forms of disqualifying rhetoric analysed in this study: ideological disqualification, where candidates critique their opponent's policies and ideologies, and identity-based disqualification, where they delegitimise their opponent's affiliations or personal characteristics.

Taking these distinct points into account, this study operationalises disqualifying rhetoric as the central concept by focusing on three dimensions: explicitness (overt vs. covert), frequency (how often disqualifying rhetoric is displayed), and type (the rhetorical form and thematic foci of the disqualification). The dimension of type is further divided into two key categories: technique (attacks vs. contrasts) and topic (policy-based vs. identity-based). These dimensions—explicitness, frequency, and type—were selected for their capacity to capture the strategic nuances of disqualifying rhetoric while ensuring analytical focus.

- Explicitness reveals the rhetorical style each candidate employed—whether through blunt disqualifications or subtler, more indirect strategies. Framing theory informs this dimension by highlighting how overt versus covert frames shape audience interpretation.
- Frequency assesses how integral disqualifying rhetoric was to a candidate's campaign narrative—whether it functioned as a core strategy or played a more supplementary role. This dimension also underscores the salience of disqualifying frames in shaping voter perceptions.
- Type examines both the techniques and topics of disqualifications. The technique evaluates whether rhetoric hostilely targets specific traits or emphasises differences between candidates to work against the other. Topic identifies the contexts in which disqualifications occurred, distinguishing between policy-focused and identity-focused ones.

While the three dimensions serve as the primary operational tools for identifying and categorising disqualifying rhetoric, the spectrum model offers a complementary conceptual lens. By situating rhetorical instances along a continuum—from covert policy contrasts to overt identity-based attacks—the model captures the intensity and polarising potential of disqualification strategies, which the categorical dimensions alone cannot fully express.

Spectrum of Disqualifying Rhetoric

Figure 1. *Spectrum of Disqualifying Rhetoric: Author's work.*

Together, the dimensions and the spectrum provide a layered framework: the dimensions break down rhetorical components for thematic coding, while the spectrum visualises how those strategies vary in their rhetorical severity and societal impact. As shown in Figure 1, rhetoric ranges from covert contrasts on policy issues to overt attacks on identity, with increasing polarising effects toward the right end of the spectrum.

Turning to the relevance of the case, this paper argues that the 2021 Peruvian presidential election offers a compelling context for studying disqualifying rhetoric due to its highly polarised nature and pronounced urban-rural divide, which was evident in much of the campaign coverage in media outlets (Celag data, 2021). The campaigns of Fujimori and Castillo exemplify how identity-based and policy-based disqualifications interact with societal cleavages, making this election an ideal case for applying the proposed framework.

Fujimori and Castillo represented sharply opposing platforms: Fujimori symbolised urban, elite continuity, while Castillo advocated for rural, marginalised communities (Asensio et al., 2021, pp. 13-14). Their campaigns reflected Peru's deep societal divides, and both relied heavily on disqualifying rhetoric as a framing strategy within negative campaigning. For instance, Fujimori used identity-based allegations, such as associating Castillo with left-wing insurgency groups (*Terruqueo*), while Castillo employed anti-elite critiques targeting *Fujimorismo* (Escárzaga, 2022, pp. 78-79). These rhetorical strategies both exploited and amplified structural divides, aligning with McCoy's conceptualisation of polarisation (McCoy, 2018, pp. 20-21). This case, therefore, offers valuable insights into how disqualifying rhetoric can reinforce polarisation, providing broader lessons for understanding the dynamics of polarised democracies worldwide.

Based on the theoretical insights of negative campaigning, polarisation, and framing theory concerning disqualifying rhetoric, this paper proposes the following hypotheses. Generally, identity-based disqualification is more prevalent in highly polarised contexts where societal divisions—such as ethnicity, class, or geography—are prominent. In such cases, candidates exploit these cleavages to frame opponents as outsiders or threats. In contrast, policy-based disqualification tends to dominate campaigns focused on governance records or ideological disqualification, where candidates critique their rivals' plans or affiliations to emphasise programmatic differences. Additionally, it argues identity-based disqualification would not only reflect societal cleavages but also act as a mechanism in charge of deepening them, transforming them into a rhetorical tool and a structural issue in polarised democracies.

In the context of the 2021 Peruvian presidential election, these broader dynamics inform specific expectations regarding the rhetorical strategies of Fujimori and Castillo. Keiko Fujimori, representing urban elites and continuity, is hypothesised to rely heavily on identity-based disqualification. Her strategy likely includes direct and recurring attacks on Castillo's identity as an Andean man and alleged ties to left-wing insurgency groups. Conversely, Pedro Castillo, as a representative of marginalised rural communities, is expected to employ a combination of policy-based disqualification—focusing on *anti-Fujimorismo* critiques—and identity-based rhetoric, targeting elites to mobilise his base and challenge entrenched power structures. These hypotheses illustrate how disqualifying rhetoric interacts with societal cleavages, shaping the polarising dynamics of the election.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employs a qualitative thematic analysis to examine the use of disqualifying rhetoric in the campaigns of Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo during the 2021 Peruvian presidential election. The analysis focuses on the transcript of a nationally televised second-round debate between the candidates, selected for its direct and confrontational nature, which fosters the emergence of disqualifying rhetoric in real-time exchanges (TvPerú Noticias, 2021). The debate provides varied discussion topics in the form of distinct blocs and a rich context for understanding how disqualifying rhetoric was strategically used to shape voter perceptions and reinforce societal cleavages during a highly polarised election (TvPerú Noticias, 2021).

The thematic analysis method is particularly well-suited to addressing the research question, “In what ways did Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo’s campaigns manifest disqualifying rhetoric?” By systematically exploring rhetorical patterns across three dimensions—explicitness, frequency, and type—this method facilitates the identification of recurring themes and variations in disqualifying rhetoric. Given the polarised nature of the election, characterised by ideological and societal divisions, thematic analysis allows for a detailed examination of how rhetorical strategies intersected with broader cleavages, such as the urban-rural divide and elite-marginalised dichotomy.

As part of the analytical framework, the study focuses on three key dimensions:

- Explicitness, which distinguishes between overt rhetoric (e.g., direct accusations or insults) and covert rhetoric (e.g., subtle implications or indirect criticisms).
- Frequency, which measures how often disqualifying rhetoric appears in each candidate’s discourse. This dimension examines whether disqualification served as a core strategy or played a supplementary role in their campaigns.
- Type, which is divided into two sub-dimensions: technique and topic. The technique sub-dimension distinguishes between attacks (aggressive targeting of traits or characteristics) and contrasts (emphasising differences between the candidates). The topic sub-dimension categorises rhetoric into policy-based (focusing on governance records, plans, or political affiliations) and identity-based (targeting personal or group characteristics such as ethnicity, class, or geographic origin).

To clarify the application of the application to the data, Table 1 offers a comparative matrix outlining how each dimension manifests in the rhetoric of the two candidates.

Dimension	Keiko Fujimori	Pedro Castillo
Explicitness	Overt rhetoric dominant: direct accusations (e.g., “Mr. Stonethrower,” ties to terrorism)	Covert contrasts preferred: Implicit critiques through body language and indirect framing
Frequency	High Frequency: Disqualifying rhetoric used consistently across most debate segments.	Moderate frequency: More strategic use, concentrated in segments like economics and corruption.
Type: Technique	Attack-focused: Personal accusations, delegitimization through inflammatory language.	Contrast-focused: Framing differences in values (e.g., work ethic, sovereignty) more than direct attacks.
Type: Topic	Identity-based: Focused on Castillo’s rural origin, gender views, insurgency ties.	Mixed (Policy + Identity): Critiques of <i>Fujimorismo</i> legacy and anti-elite identity-based rhetoric.

Table 1. Comparative Use of Disqualifying Rhetoric by Fujimori and Castillo. Source: Author’s Work.

The study’s analysis compares Fujimori and Castillo’s use of disqualifying rhetoric within each dimension, highlighting similarities and differences in their rhetorical strategies. Additionally, these themes are evaluated in relation to societal and ideological polarization, exploring how disqualifying rhetoric aligned

with and reinforced cleavages such as the urban-rural divide, elite-marginalized dynamics, and ideological oppositions.

While thematic analysis provides a nuanced framework for examining rhetorical strategies, it is not without limitations. Coding subjectivity poses a potential challenge, as the interpretation of disqualifying rhetoric may vary. To address this, the study follows a transparent and replicable coding process to ensure methodological rigour. Additionally, while the findings may not be generalizable to other contexts, the insights derived from this case study offer contributions to research on polarised democracies and negative campaigning.

By applying this method, the research seeks to provide a systematic understanding of disqualifying rhetoric in polarized elections, demonstrating how it influences voter perceptions and deepens societal divisions. Furthermore, the findings contribute to broader literature on negative campaigning, polarization, and framing theory, with particular relevance to electoral politics in Latin American democracies.

ANALYSIS

This analysis examines the ways in which disqualifying rhetoric was employed during the presidential campaigns of Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo. The findings reveal that both candidates used distinct strategies to undermine each other, reflecting broader political and societal tensions. Four main themes emerged from the analysis: Fujimori's overt identity-based disqualification targeting Castillo's identity; Castillo's use of covert contrast disqualification; both candidates' critique of past governments; and the pervasive disqualification surrounding corruption accusations.

These themes illuminate the polarised nature of the campaign, where each candidate's rhetoric not only framed their opponent negatively but also appealed to specific voter bases. By leveraging identity, governance failures, and ethical integrity, both candidates sought to resonate with voters' frustrations and fears. Moreover, the prevalence of disqualifying rhetoric underscores the role of polarisation in shaping political discourse, as the campaigns focused less on substantive policies and more on delegitimising the opposition.

Theme 1: Fujimori's Overt Identity-Based Disqualification Attacks

From the start of the debate, Keiko Fujimori adopted a direct and confrontational rhetorical style, targeting Pedro Castillo's identity and values. Her disqualification tactics emphasised his association with class struggle narratives, accusations of violent behaviour, and alignment with rural, traditionalist values. These strategies aimed to delegitimise Castillo's credibility and position Fujimori as a stable and modern alternative.

In her opening statement, Fujimori accused Castillo's supporters of violence and sabotage by throwing stones, framing his rhetoric as divisive and rooted in hatred:

He later speaks of dictatorship. I think you have not heard Mr. Bermejo, that they want to get in power and stay. Do you watch the news? Seems like you don't, Mr. Pedro Stonethrower. Stop spreading all these lies.

By calling Castillo "Tirapiedras" (stone thrower), Fujimori linked him to rural Peruvians (such as Andeans) and working-class individuals' ways of protest, symbolising chaos and hypocrisy. She contrasted this with her narrative of stability, further reinforced by mentioning Guillermo Bermejo, a party member whose controversial comments on power painted Castillo as either complicit or naive.

Fujimori also critiqued Castillo's gender rhetoric, tying it to outdated values associated with his rural background. Highlighting his exclusive references to men in discussions of work policies, she remarked:

Mr. Pedro Castillo only makes references to men, "men are breadwinners." Show some more respect to women...

This positioned Castillo as embodying machismo and failing to recognise women's contributions. Fujimori, in turn, framed herself as a defender of gender equality, addressing an issue increasingly important in Peru.

Throughout the debate, Fujimori's rhetorical strategy consistently linked Castillo to violence, hypocrisy, and traditionalist values. By emphasising these contrasts, she sought to disqualify Castillo as a credible leader while positioning herself as stable, modern, and inclusive to appeal to a broader electorate. This form of rhetoric aligns with the far right of the spectrum model (see Figure 1), representing overt identity-based disqualification that draws on deeply polarising themes

Theme 2: Castillo's Use Of Covert Contrast Disqualification

Pedro Castillo often employed covert disqualification tactics, avoiding direct references to his rival, Keiko Fujimori, or her affiliations. Throughout the debate, particularly in the Economics and Employment block, Castillo balanced his critiques across policy and identity dimensions, using tone and body language to subtly frame contrasts. For instance, Castillo remarked:

We believe it's important to acknowledge that labor brings wealth. Therefore, those of us who know how to work (emphasis), we must sustain entrepreneurial people. Peru is a country of entrepreneurs.

Here, Castillo emphasises the value of labour, implicitly contrasting hardworking individuals with those benefiting from inherited privilege. The phrase "*los que sabemos trabajar*" (us who know how to work) subtly critiques elites, hinting at Fujimori's ties to her father's political legacy. By aligning himself with the working class, Castillo frames Fujimori's identity as disconnected from Peru's broader struggles.

Another example highlights sovereignty and resource management:

Peru must be for peruvians. I do not bring promise bouquets (emphasis, subtle glance at rival), I bring to you this fighting spirit, as a patrolman, as a worker who knows how to run things.

Here, Castillo contrasts his authenticity and practical experience with Fujimori's perceived superficial promises in her policies. The phrase "*I do not bring promise bouquets*" suggests his proposals are rooted in lived realities, while his tone and subtle gestures reinforce the critique.

By using indirect rhetoric, Castillo disqualifies Fujimori without overt attacks, framing her as out of touch with ordinary Peruvians. His strategic use of contrasts deepens societal divides, amplifying the election's polarising dynamics. Castillo's rhetoric in these examples is situated closer to the centre-left of the spectrum, falling under covert identity-based and policy-based contrasts. His indirect critiques leverage social identity without overt attacks.

Theme 3: Mutual Critique Of The Latest Government

While this paper has consistently observed polarising rhetoric from both candidates on various topics, there is a notable instance where subtle agreement emerged in the form of disqualification aimed at a larger actor: the previous government. This shared rhetoric centred on criticism of the administration's handling of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the candidates did not explicitly demonstrate unity or amity, their mutual denouncement of the government's actions and its consequences reflected a less polarising approach to addressing urgent health matters. Instead of clashing over what was relevant, both candidates expressed similar concerns about improving the welfare of health workers.

Pedro Castillo, for instance, criticised the precarious working conditions of health staff under CAS (administrative services contracts), remarking:

... No more CAS to health workers and other workplace aggressions. We must recognize labor as fundamental, the right to work must be respected.

For context, CAS refers to temporary work agreements outside the public career or private activity frameworks, governed by a distinct decree (SUNAT 2022). Castillo frames these contracts as emblematic of labour precarity, arguing that health workers under CAS are often denied proper access to their rights. While the government justified its actions during the pandemic as necessary under desperate circumstances, Castillo advocates for abolishing CAS to secure better rights for workers and reinforce his anti-elite discourse.

Similarly, Keiko Fujimori expressed her position on CAS contracts in the following statement:

In Fuerza Popular, we support from our seats in congress the abolition of CAS. Unfortunately the government and the executive have been ignoring this rule but everyone on CAS in the health sector knows our position perfectly well.

Here, Fujimori highlights her party's efforts in Congress to abolish CAS, lamenting the government's refusal to approve the initiative. Although her reasoning is less explicitly framed than Castillo's, she emphasises her support for health workers, referencing their awareness of her party's stance. This aligns with Castillo's critique, as both candidates highlight the need for improved working conditions in the health sector while disqualifying the previous government's actions around health workers and the pandemic.

Theme 4: Pervasive Overt Disqualification Attacks Under Corruption Accusations

Given Peru's history with political corruption, both candidates used the debate's anti-corruption segment to escalate their disqualifying rhetoric. Nevertheless, corruption was alluded to from time to time within other segments when both candidates wished to directly attack each other. Pedro Castillo, contrasted with his recurrent covert style, adopted a direct, overt style, criticising Fujimorismo and its corrupt legacy. Keiko Fujimori, in turn, focused on linking Castillo and his party to corruption and left-wing insurgency through targeted attacks on Vladimir Cerrón, Castillo's party leader. It is also interesting to note that this segment got quite tense to the point where one of the moderators reminded both candidates about the purpose of the debate being to highlight policies rather than attack their rival.

Castillo posed rhetorical questions to the audience:

Do you not think that speaking of corruption is synonymous with Fujimorismo? Do you not think that to speak of corruption you should have at least a pinch of morals? (slight chuckle).

Here, Castillo ties corruption to Fujimori's identity and legacy, referencing her legal troubles with money laundering allegations. The rhetorical questions undermine her credibility by framing her as hypocritical for addressing corruption while facing unresolved charges, positioning Castillo as a cleaner alternative with no political baggage. Fujimori countered with:

Yes, Mr. Cerrón... Oh, sorry, Mr. Castillo (slightly amused). He speaks of proposals to incapacitate public officials. A lot of these norms have been supported by Fuerza Popular in congress, where civil death and impediments for corrupt people and terrorists (emphasis) to become officials were passed. And that is the reason why your political dad (party leader) was not here in the first place...

Fujimori conflates Castillo with Cerrón, framing him as a puppet for a corrupt party. By highlighting her party's anti-corruption legislation, she distances herself from her scandals while disqualifying Castillo as unfit to lead. Additionally, her reference to terrorism, commonly used by right-wing sympathizers to undermine left-wing sympathizers (*Terruqueo*), further ties Castillo to Peru's insurgent past. While both candidates escalate their rhetoric here, Castillo's framing of Fujimorismo's corruption occupies the overt policy-attack range, while Fujimori's response combining corruption and insurgency references straddles both overt policy and overt identity-based territory.

Type of Disqualification	Sub-Type	Candidate	Example	Dimension
Identity-Based	Overt Attack	Fujimori	“Mr. Pedro Stonethrower... Stop spreading lies.” (References to rural protest tactics & insurgency)	Identity / Overt / Attack
Identity-Based	Covert Contrast	Castillo	“Those of us who know how to work...” (Implies disconnect between elites and working class)	Identity / Covert / Contrast
Policy-Based	Overt Attack	Castillo	“Speaking of corruption is synonymous with Fujimorismo... You should have a pinch of morals.”	Policy / Overt / Attack
Policy-Based	Covert Contrast	Castillo	“I do not bring promise bouquets... I bring the spirit of a patrolman.” (Critique of elite-style campaigning)	Policy / Covert / Contrast
Identity-Based	Overt Attack	Fujimori	“Mr. Pedro Castillo only makes references to men... Show more respect to women.”	Identity / Overt / Attack
Policy-Based	Overt Attack	Fujimori	“That’s why your political dad [Cerrón] is not here today.” (Links Castillo to party corruption)	Policy / Overt / Attack

Table 2. Typology of Disqualifying Rhetoric in the 2021 Peruvian Presidential Debate. Source: Author’s Work.

To consolidate the findings from the thematic analysis, Table 2 offers a typology of disqualifying rhetoric used by both candidates. It categorises each rhetorical instance by topic (identity vs. policy), technique (attack vs. contrast), and style (overt vs. covert), supported by quotes from the debate.

POST-DEBATE SHIFTS AND ENDURING IMPACT OF DISQUALIFYING RHETORIC

While the 2021 presidential debate between Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo did not result in dramatic swings in voting intention, post-debate polling reveals subtle yet significant effects of disqualifying rhetoric—particularly *Terruqueo*, or identity-based attacks linking opponents to terrorism. In the final week of May, just before the debate, multiple polls indicated a statistical tie between the candidates. A Datum survey from May 27 showed Castillo with 42.6% of voter support and Fujimori with 41.7%, constituting a near deadlock (La República, 2021).

However, by May 30–31, a poll by Ipsos recorded a modest recovery in Castillo’s numbers: 51.1% for Castillo versus 48.9% for Fujimori (El Bocón, 2021). While these changes may reflect general campaign dynamics, the IEP analysis from this period noted that Fujimori’s *Terruqueo* campaign had contributed to a visible decline in voter identification with the political left (IEP, 2021). This suggests that her overt identity-based disqualification strategy—particularly linking Castillo to radical insurgency movements—had the unintended consequence of reorienting voters ideologically, even if it did not definitively change vote margins.

These findings support this study’s argument that disqualifying rhetoric, especially when framed through identity and fear-based associations, can extend its influence beyond immediate electoral outcomes. By reducing ideological identification with the left, Fujimori’s rhetoric subtly reshaped the political landscape, illustrating how campaign discourse can have structural effects on voter perception and polarisation in fragile democracies.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the disqualifying rhetoric employed by Keiko Fujimori and Pedro Castillo during the 2021 Peruvian presidential election, testing the hypothesis that Fujimori, as a representative of elite continuity, would predominantly use identity-based disqualification, while Castillo would focus on both policy and identity-based disqualification to critique elite structures. The findings supported these

hypotheses, showing that Fujimori's rhetoric weaponised xenophobic undertones and accusations tied to historical insurgency, targeting Castillo's identity to delegitimise him. Meanwhile, Castillo's campaign leaned on anti-elite narratives and critiques of Fujimorismo, reflecting and reinforcing longstanding societal cleavages such as the urban-rural divide and class-based inequalities.

The broader implications of these findings provide a deeper understanding of how disqualifying rhetoric functions in polarised democracies, extending the debates introduced in this study's introduction. Although the debate did not dramatically shift overall vote intentions and remained as a technical tie, survey data from the Institute of Peruvian Studies (IEP) suggests that Keiko Fujimori's *Terruqueo* campaign had a measurable effect in shaping political identities (IEP, 2021, pp. 1-3). Specifically, IEP noted a reduction in voter identification with the political left following her overt identity-based disqualification of Castillo through insurgency associations (IEP, 2021). This suggests that disqualification—particularly when leveraging stigmatised historical narratives—can influence public opinion in ways that transcend electoral margins, contributing to the reconfiguration of political alignment and deepening ideological cleavages.

These dynamics illuminate the role of disqualifying rhetoric as both a reflection of and a contributor to polarisation. While such rhetoric can be effective in mobilising political bases, its consequences extend beyond the immediate campaign. By amplifying societal cleavages, disqualifying rhetoric deepens polarisation, complicating efforts to foster post-electoral reconciliation. The Peruvian case demonstrates that this rhetoric does not merely exploit existing divisions but actively entrenches them, posing risks to democratic cohesion. This raises broader questions about the role of political rhetoric in polarised democracies: Could these systems withstand the divisive effects of identity-based attacks? What measures might mitigate the damage caused by such strategies to democratic stability?

Through the lens of framing theory, this study demonstrated how candidates strategically choose between identity- and policy-based disqualification to align with societal cleavages. Such strategies highlight the interplay between polarisation and negative rhetoric, suggesting that democracies with similarly entrenched divisions may face comparable challenges in future elections. These findings underscore the urgent need to address the structural vulnerabilities that make polarised societies particularly susceptible to the harmful effects of disqualifying rhetoric.

Moreover, the disqualification rhetoric employed was not limited to the electoral event. During the post-electoral period both candidates and their supporters continued to engage in delegitimising discourse—Fujimori and her camp questioned the integrity of the electoral process and specifically blamed Andean populations—while Castillo's rhetoric reinforced anti-elite identity narratives (The Washington Post, 2021). These continuities highlight how polarising rhetoric during campaigns may undermine democratic trust and governability even after the ballots were counted.

These findings offer insights not just into Peru's political climate, but into broader regional trends where disqualifying rhetoric serves as a powerful vehicle for mobilisation in polarised democracies. In Brazil, for example, Jair Bolsonaro frequently deployed anti-leftist rhetoric by framing the Workers' Party as a threat to national stability, socialism, and traditional values—tactics that mirrored *Terruqueo* strategies in Peru (Hunter & Power, 2019). In Venezuela, Nicolás Maduro has systematically framed opposition leaders as agents of foreign intervention and elite corruption, deepening ideological divides and undermining democratic legitimacy (Corrales, 2015). Similarly, in Nicaragua, Daniel Ortega has branded dissenters as “terrorists,” criminalising opposition discourse and collapsing political pluralism (Freedom House, 2021). These examples suggest that identity- and ideology-based disqualification is increasingly central to political contestation in Latin America, underscoring the need to examine rhetorical strategies not merely as campaign tools but as mechanisms that entrench polarisation and authoritarian drift.

Ultimately, this study highlights the dual role of disqualifying rhetoric as both a product of societal divisions and a mechanism that exacerbates them. Understanding these dynamics is essential for fostering healthier political discourse and mitigating the risks posed by polarization. The 2021 Peruvian presidential election offers a cautionary example of how rhetoric designed to delegitimize opponents can have far-reaching consequences, leaving lasting marks on democratic cohesion.

Luciana Antonella Barreto

REFERENCES

- Asensio, Camacho, González, Grompone, Moscoso, Teves, ... & Vásquez (2021). El profe: cómo Pedro Castillo se convirtió en presidente del Perú y qué pasará a continuación (Vol. 66). Instituto de Estudios Peruanos.
- Burt (2006). "Quien Habla es Terrorista:" The Political Use of Fear in Fujimori 's Peru', *Latin American Research Review*, 41(3), pp. 32-62.
- Celag data (2021). "Preelectoral Perú: antesala de una jornada histórica," <https://www.celag.org/preelectoral-peru-antesala-de-una-jornada-historica/>. (Consulted on December 14 2024).
- Corrales (2015). Autocratic legalism in Venezuela. *Journal of Democracy*, 26(2), pp. 37-51.
- Dargent Bocanegra and Rousseau (2021) Perú 2020: ¿El quiebre de la continuidad? *Revista de Ciencia Política* (Santiago), 41(2), pp. 377-400.
- Dassonneville and Çakır (2021). Party system polarization and electoral behavior. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*.
- El Bocón (2021) "Encuesta Ipsos: Último sondeo entre Keiko y Castillo," <https://elbocon.pe/trends/encuesta-ipsos-ultimo-sondeo-entre-keiko-y-castillo>. (Accessed on 12 April 2025).
- Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of communication*, 43(4), pp. 51-58.
- Escárzaga (2022). La elección de Pedro Castillo: polarización, racismo y "terruqueo" en las elecciones presidenciales. *Anuario Latinoamericano-Ciencias Políticas y Relaciones Internacionales*, 13(1), pp. 77-91.
- France24 (2021). "Keiko contra Castillo: Perú decidirá entre el fujimorismo y la izquierda radical ortodoxa," <https://www.france24.com/es/am%C3%A9rica-latina/20210417-keiko-castillo-peru-fujimorismo-izquierda>. (Accessed on December 18 2024).
- Freedom House. (2021). *Freedom in the World 2021: Nicaragua*, <https://freedomhouse.org/country/nicaragua/freedom-world/2021>. (Accessed on April 12 2025).
- Haselmayer M. (2019). Negative campaigning and its consequences: a review and a look ahead. *French Politics*, 17, pp. 355-372.
- Hunter and Power (2019). Bolsonaro and Brazil's illiberal backlash. *Journal of Democracy*, 30(1), pp. 68-82.
- IEP (Instituto de Estudios Peruanos) (2021). "Intención de voto y aprobación presidencial - Mayo III," <https://iep.org.pe/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Informe-IEP-OP-mayo-III-2021-intencion-de-voto-y-aprobacion-presidencial.pdf>. (Accessed on April 12 2025).
- Iyengar, Lelkes, Levendusky, Malhotra, & Westwood (2019). The origins and consequences of affective polarization in the United States. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 22(1), pp. 129-146.
- Jamieson, Waldman, Sherr (2000). Eliminate the negative? Categories of analysis for political advertisements. In *Crowded Airwaves*, ed. JA Thurber, CJ Nelson, DA Dulio, 44-64. Washington DC: Brookings Inst.
- Jost, Baldassarri, & Druckman (2022). Cognitive-motivational mechanisms of political polarization in social-communicative contexts. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1(10), pp. 560-576.
- La República (2021). "Datum: Castillo tiene 42,6% de preferencia electoral y Fujimori alcanza un 41,7%," <https://larepublica.pe/elecciones/2021/05/28/datum-pedro-castillo-tiene-426-de-preferencia-electoral-y-keiko-fujimori-alcanza-un-417-mdga>. (Accessed on April 12 2025).
- Lau and Rovner (2009). Negative campaigning. *Annual review of political science*, 12(1), pp. 285-306.
- Rekker (2021). The nature and origins of political polarization over science. *Public Understanding of Science*, 30(4), pp. 352-368.
- Slater M.D. (2007). Reinforcing spirals: The mutual influence of media selectivity and media effects and their impact on individual behavior and social identity. *Communication theory*, 17(3), pp. 281-303.
- SUNAT (Superintendencia nacional de Aduanas y Admisión Tributaria) (2022). "Contrato Administrativo de Servicios (CAS)," <https://orientacion.sunat.gob.pe/07-contrato-administrativo-de-servicios-cas>. (Accessed on December 19 2024).
- TVPerú Noticias (2021). "Debate presidencial" TVPerú, 31 May.
- The Washington Post (2021). "Pedro Castillo podría vencer a la derecha peruana, pero no a su racismo," <https://www.washingtonpost.com/es/post-opinion/2021/06/13/elecciones-peru-2021-racismo-keiko-fujimori-pedro-castillo-fraude/>. (Accessed on April 12 2025).

APPENDIX I:

CODE BOOK:

Name	Definition	Example
Overt	manifestation of explicit rhetoric including naming, accusations, mention of political spectrums	“it is essential to complete the hospitals that were left unfinished by different regional governments, especially those on the left. ”
Covert	manifestation of implicit rhetoric including indirect criticism and subtle implications)	“It is a lie what they say : we are going to close your store , that we are going to take away your bread...”
Disqualification	Criticism towards anyone other than the candidate speaking	“ I would like my opponent, for the first time in history, to apologize to the women who were sterilized...”
Non Disqualification	Personal sponsor and general discussions of debate related content	“Today I come to give proposals, proposals to push our country forward”
Attack	aggressive targeting of traits or characteristics of the opponent or what he thinks or discusses	“Do you watch the news? It seems not, Mr. Pedro Stonethrower . Stop telling so many lies...”
Contrast	emphasizing differences between the candidates	“I come here with clean hands (emphasis on the last word, subtle glance at rival)...”
Policy-based	focusing on governance records, plans, or political affiliations	“ we must implement a thousand ICU beds in order to also provide intermediate care with high-flow cannulas and oxygen concentrators”
Identity-based	focusing on group characteristics such as ethnicity, class, or geographic origin	“You, Mr. Pedro Castillo, with your language and hatred messages filled with division and class struggle... you are used to throwing stones”

APPENDIX II:Click here for [Debate transcript in English and Spanish](#)